

Deliverable 1.1

Quality Assurance Handbook

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Table of Contents

<i>List of Figures</i>	6
<i>List of Tables</i>	6
<i>List of Abbreviations</i>	7
1. Executive Summary	8
2. Brief introduction to the GREAT project	9
3. Management Structure	9
3.1. Work Package (WP)	11
3.2. Project Management Committee (PMC)	11
3.3. General Assembly (GA)	13
3.4. Scientific Committee	13
3.5. Consortium Agreement (CA)	14
4. Quality Assurance Procedures and Code of Conduct	14
4.1. Internal communication structures and procedures	15
4.2. External communication structures & procedures	16
4.3. Quality of deliverables and peer reviews	16
4.4. Quality of non-deliverables	19
4.5. Internal Surveys	20
4.6. Risk Management	20
4.7. Project Templates	23
5. Tools and Collaboration Infrastructure	23
6. Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)	24
6.1. What is RRI?	24
6.2. Governance	25
6.3. Open access	25
6.4. Ethics	26
6.5. Data Protection and Privacy	27
6.6. Communication Strategy	28
6.7. National and Local Regulations and Standards	29
6.8. Gender	29
6.9. Education	30

6.10. Public Engagement	31
6.11. RRI management in GREAT	31
7. <i>Open Access and Open Research Data</i>.....	32
7.1. Open access strategy for publications and other artifacts	33
7.2. Open access and open data handling process	34
8. <i>Closing remarks</i>.....	35
9. <i>References</i>.....	36
10. <i>Annex I – Confidentiality Agreement and Data Exchange Form ...</i>	37
10.1. Confidentiality Agreement.....	37
10.2. Data Exchange Form.....	38
10.3. Data Sharing Agreement Template and instructions for use	39
11. <i>Annex II – Checklist for Deliverables</i>.....	51
12. <i>Annex III Peer Review Template</i>	53
13. <i>Annex IV – Consent Form</i>	54

List of Figures

Figure 1: Overview of key dimensions 25

List of Tables

Table 1: Executive Management Board 10

Table 2: Assigned Work Package Leaders 11

Table 3: Partner project managers..... 12

Table 4: Scientific Committee members..... 13

Table 5: GREAT critical risks..... 22

List of Abbreviations

CA	Consortium Agreement
CO	Confidential
DIH	Digital Innovation Hub
DI	Digital Innovation
DMP	Data Management Plan
DoA	Description of Action
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EMB	Executive Management Board
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
EGE	The European Group on Ethics in Science and New Technologies
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulations
GREAT	Games Realising Effective Affective Transformation
H2020	Horizon 2020 program of the European Union
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
PMC	Project Management Committee
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
SC	Scientific Committee
UKRI	United Kingdom Research & Innovation
WP	Work Package

1. Executive Summary

This Project Handbook describes the internal procedures of the GREAT consortium in terms of management structures as well as quality assurance measures. It also defines the way the partners are dealing with Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI), especially considering ethical issues related to personal data collection, analysis and storage. Open source and open access are important elements of the project program itself as well as of the consortium's RRI strategy. The way in which these aspects are dealt with is reflected in the open research data management plan, which is briefly addressed here and is presented in detail in D1.2 Research Data Management Plan.

The main target group for this deliverable is the consortium partners themselves as this handbook defines the project internal processes for securing high quality research work to be performed across a set of complementary partner institutions. It serves as a reference document for all GREAT team members including individuals joining in the project at a later stage.

Since the project brings together a set of experts from different fields and backgrounds, a core principle guiding internal processes is open participation and flexibility. Transparency regarding the project status, as well as risk recognition, are additional principles that the project partners are committed to.

However, in order to operate effectively in a distributed team, procedures have been defined to optimise communication and collaboration in the consortium. Regular meetings are held via web-conference, with communication also conducted via e-mail and the project mailing list. The main tools for sharing and collaborating on documents are Gitlab Wiki and Google Drive. For sharing any sensitive data, NextCloud will be used.

The consortium is committed to producing high quality project outcomes and deliverables and thus quality control is important. Quality guidelines describe the internal peer review process, which is applied to all project deliverables. To assure quality in our internal collaboration process, short internal surveys or reflection sessions may be carried out, normally in connection with project meetings. These instruments are intended as a self-reflection and self-evaluation tools for the whole group to examine project structures and processes.

In terms of ethics, the consortium will follow the general rules defined by the EC and commits strongly to respect the individual and their privacy at all times. Templates have been prepared for informed consent as well as the exchange of primary research data amongst partners that may contain personal data from study participants. The ethics requirements also consider personal data collection,

processing, and storage to be in line with the GDPR and the data exchange between EU and third countries. Raising awareness about related RRI issues is of concern for the management and is regularly stressed.

Finally, openness is a core value of the project and thus the consortium is looking into open strategies with regards to its research and innovation outcomes. This relates to software that is published under specific open licenses, following and where possible contributing to open standards, as well as the research publications, which should be made openly accessible as widely as possible.

This handbook is maintained as a living document and is updated as the need arises in order to improve the internal processes.

2. Brief introduction to the GREAT project

Research and innovation in the GREAT project will provide new insights into the role of the games industry and non-commercial creative practices in the EU for the benefit of society. Our research will provide insights into the impact of Citizen Science Games on European society by conducting case studies that show how games affect citizen participation in European society. Evidence-based proposals and guidance will show how games can promote social cohesion through improved dialogue between citizens and political actors. They will make an important contribution to democracy education and help promote social engagement and low-threshold political participation of citizens in the EU and partner countries. Up to date details of GREAT activities are available on the project website www.greatproject.gg

3. Management Structure

Both the Grant Agreement (GA) and the Consortium Agreement (CA) specify a number of bodies for the management of the project. The following sections specify the operational view of these bodies, but it should be remembered that the GA and CA, as legal documents, take precedence over this handbook.

GREAT is a large-scale innovation action project aiming at a wide community on a global scale, with a special focus on Europe. Therefore, the management structure and procedures work in a flexible manner in order to:

- Achieve integration of all consortium members and mobilization of their expertise, knowledge, and networks in every stage of the project
- Efficiently coordinate the processing of the work plan in a collaborative environment

- Continuously involve contextual expertise and knowledge of relevant stakeholders from local innovation hubs and their networks

Our approach is a combination of integration and decentralization strategies. Integration is achieved through the composition of a consortium with complementary skills and knowledge, the development of a joint framework, the agreement on common guidelines for co-design activities, the joint work on the platform and community development, and project workshops and meetings. The resources of all partners will be mobilized by decentralization of responsibilities through the assignment of leadership for work packages and defined work package tasks with a clear task-sharing based on the different competence fields of the partners.

The management structure defines the basic roles and responsibilities. The Executive Management Board (EMB) has the decision-making power of the consortium, the Terms of Reference are currently work-in-progress and will be approved by the EMB. The Project Management Committee (PMC), which comprises the Editorial Committee formulated in D6.2, will follow scientific and operational guidance from the EMB and is responsible for the overall administrative actions of the project. The EMB has the authority to make decisions relating to the legal and financial aspects of the project. The board members provide research leadership and are responsible for steering the research activities being carried out by the consortium so that these activities align with those proposed in the grant agreement. It is suggested that the Board members review project progress and many of these members are in the PMC, where co-monitoring of project progress exists on a bi-weekly basis. Board members will meet when important decisions relating to the project need to be made.

Partner	Board Member
DIPF	Prof. Hendrik Drachsler
UNIR	Prof. Daniel Burgos
SIG	Dr. Simon Egenfeldt-Nielsen
ZSI	Dr. Barbara Kieslinger
UoB	Prof. Paul Hollins
PM	Ms. Jude Ower
FU	Dr. Aravella Zachariou

Table 1: Executive Management Board

3.1. Work Package (WP)

The work package (WP) is the building block of the project. The WP leader

- organizes the WP and coordinates the different tasks,
- prepares and chairs WP meetings,
- organizes the production of the results of the WP,
- represents the WP in the Executive Management Board.

work package has been appointed a Work Package Leader who is responsible for the progress within the work package and who assists the project manager (Dr. Jane Yau) in the strategic coordination of the innovation actions of the project. The WP Leader is supported by task leaders and other members of the consortium involved in each of the WPs. Clear responsibilities based on the competences of each partner are described in the Work Package Description. Current WP leaders are shown in Table 2.

Work Package	Lead partner	Name
WP1 - Project Management & Coordination	DIPF	Dr. Jane Yau
WP2 - Intervention Design	UNIR	Prof. David Griffiths
WP3 - Technical Development & Repurposing Games	SGI	Dr. Simon Egenfeldt-Nielsen
WP4 - Case Studies & Research Outputs	UoB	Prof. Paul Hollins
WP5 - Evaluation, Impact, Future Implications	ZSI	Dr. Barbara Kieslinger
WP6 - Engagement, Dissemination, and Sustainability	PM	Ms. Lou Fawcett

Table 2: Assigned Work Package Leaders

3.2. Project Management Committee (PMC)

The project is managed through the Project Management Committee (PMC). It provides the overall direction for the project, both strategic and operational. The PMC maintains the direction and activities of the project and obtains advice from the Work Package Leaders, to ensure that the project meets its stated and implied goals. The

PMC ultimately supervises all project management processes, including initiation, planning, execution, control, and closure of project phases. Within this framework, the Work Package Leaders coordinate the detailed planning, execution, and control of the technical tasks to meet scientific and technical objectives of the project as relevant to their work packages.

The PMC is responsible for the proper execution and implementation of the decisions of the General Assembly and makes suggestions to the General Assembly on a pending decision such as:

- Accept or reject changes to the work plan, changes in the Grant Agreement, and amendments to the Consortium Agreement
- Make changes in the Project Management structure

The PMC is chaired by the Program Manager and is composed of the Work Package Leaders plus a representative from partners not leading a work package. The PMC is currently composed of the persons listed in Table 3 below. Associate Partners are invited to attend meetings as non-voting members.

Partner	Short name	Partner Project Manager
Dipf Leibniz-Institut Für Bildungsforschung Und Bildungsinformation	DIPF	Dr. Jane Yau
Serious Games Interactive	SGI	Dr. Simon Egenfeldt-Nielsen
Zentrum Fur Soziale Innovation GmbH	ZSI	Dr. Barbara Kieslinger
Universidad Internacional De La Rioja SA	UNIR	Mr. Joaquín Alonso
Frederick University	FU	Dr. Aravella Zachariou
The University of Bolton	UoB	Prof. Paul Hollins
Playmob Limited	PM	Ms. Lou Fawcett
Northwest University (Associate Partner)	ZA	Prof. Dorothy Laubscher
Beijing Normal University (Associate Partner)	China	Dr. Tingwen Chang

Table 3: Partner project managers

3.3. General Assembly (GA)

At least once per year a General Assembly (GA), consisting of the consortium members will take place. The General Assembly is obligatory for the Project Management Committee, which consists of all WP leaders and partners. The goal of the GA is to ensure the smooth running of the project, the integration of each work package, and the enabling of the work in progress by setting the next tasks for the consortium members. The responsibilities of the various parties are described in more detail below. The GA will take place in connection to events hosted by consortium members or strongly connected to the project. Associate Partners are invited to attend the assembly in a non-voting capacity.

Decisions taken during the General Assembly include the content of the grant agreement, finances, and intellectual property rights. This body also has the right to decide on the evolution of the partnership (e.g., entry of new partner), and the project as such (e.g., termination of the project). If needed, an extraordinary General Assembly meeting can be called at any time upon written request (including electronically via e-mail) of any Member of the Executive Management Board.

3.4. Scientific Committee

The Scientific Committee (SC) is a group of persons drawn from among project staff. The SC is managed in WP4 and it will be consulted for important decisions that affect the direction of research and/or are related to the adoption of the results from the GREAT project. The terms of reference of the SC are currently work in progress, and will be approved by the EMB.

SC members	Affiliation
Prof. Paul Hollins	UoB
Dr. Celestine Iwendi	UoB
Katharina Koller	ZSI
Prof. Hendrik Drachsler	DIPF
Prof. David Griffiths	UNIR
Dr. Aravella Zachariou	FU
Dr. Simon Egenfeldt-Nielsen	SGI
Ms. Jude Ower	PM

Table 4: Scientific Committee members

The SC members are listed in Table 4. This is the confirmed membership at the time of writing, and the membership list may in future be extended with the addition of more experts. Each partner institution has only one vote in the SC, however many representatives they may have. Associate Partners may be invited to participate in the committee in a non-voting capacity. The SC makes recommendations to the consortium and ensures that all academic outputs maintain consistent academic quality standards in respect of ethics, integrity and rigour and ensure that all outputs fully comply with the requirements set out in the grant agreement.

Ethical issues within the project will be examined within the Scientific Committee, which may have additional representatives from associate partners. The ethics committees of individual partners may make the ethical requirements more demanding, but not relax them. This principle is particularly important in the case of associate partners in China and in South Africa, where ethical requirements for data collection may be more permissive than in Europe, and the informed consent process less well established. No data will be transferred from Europe to third countries, and any data imported to Europe will be previously anonymised.

3.5. Consortium Agreement (CA)

Before the start of the project, a consortium agreement was signed by all partners. It defines the specific operational procedures for the different project bodies described above. This includes, amongst other aspects, the responsibilities of the parties and their liabilities towards each other as well as the governance structure, financial provision, and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) issues. The consortium agreement also describes the decision-making structures and defines the General Assembly as the ultimate decision-making body.

4. Quality Assurance Procedures and Code of Conduct

Quality assurance is of high priority in collaborative research, such as GREAT, and the consortium is committed to a set of quality procedures to guarantee high quality project output. Measures to ensure good quality include the definition of internal communication structures, regular internal reflections on risks as well as a defined peer review process for any project deliverable. The specific procedures will be described in more detail in the following sections.

4.1. Internal communication structures and procedures

Internal communication is first and foremost based on the concept of openness and transparency. An active communication strategy is implemented to establish a strong project identity and thereby obtain maximum transparency for all partners involved, and increased synergy in cooperation.

Daily communication among the WPs, the partners, etc. is established mainly through the following:

- e-mails and a central mailing list including all project partners
- a shared Gitlab Wiki project management tool for file sharing, project management and daily communication
- a project space hosted at the DIPF Nextcloud for internal exchange and online storage of all documents that contain any sensitive data, or large files such as videos: https://cloud.educs-hosting.net/apps/files/?dir=/EU_GREAT&fileid=1003036
- A project Google Drive which is GDPR-compliant for European and UK partners
- Web-conferencing (Zoom) for regular online meetings,
- Face-to-face communication (during annual presential project meetings).

The consortium partners meet approximately every year face-to-face (at synchronization points) to coordinate the progress. Every two weeks, at least one virtual consortium meeting takes place via web-conferencing. These meetings ensure internal communication of the Project Management Committee among partners, allow the WP Leaders (WP1: Dr. Jane Yau, WP2: Prof. David Griffiths, WP3: Dr. Simon Egenfeldt-Nielsen, WP4: Prof. Paul Hollins, WP5: Dr. Barbara Kieslinger and WP6: Ms. Jude Ower) to coordinate the various tasks, and report the progress of work to the team members.

Following the meetings, minutes are compiled and circulated to all partners on the Wiki, for later consultation. Each team reports on the latest updates before the meeting in a shared document, all participants are invited to receive an update before the meeting starts and the most relevant issues are then discussed during the meetings. The protocols, which do not include any sensitive information, are available on the Wiki section - <https://gitlab.educs-hosting.net/eu-great/project-management/-/wikis/meetings-2023>

In addition to these virtual consortium meetings, working groups within and across the WPs are established in the course of project work, and virtual meetings are organized by those groups. Minutes and recordings of these meetings are made available as appropriate on the Gitlab Wiki and Nextcloud.

WP 4 Case Studies and Research Outputs takes a research leadership role in coordinating research activities throughout the project, in line with the central importance of methodological aspects of the activities of the project which are within the remit of WP4. WP2 leads intervention design and WP5 focuses on evaluation. UoB, Leader of WP4, will ensure that involvement in the research process will be made as easy as possible for all participating partners. Participants for research activities will be identified within partner organization and the associate partners, and particularly from among the students and lecturers of the academic partners. As well as this, we will make extensive use of the policy stakeholder networks of partners and of associate partners. In order to increase the research and policy impact of the project, we aim to apply the research activities in authentic conditions at scale, which are of genuine value to policy stakeholders, who are connected to project and associate partners. Associate partners will also be invited to establish inquiries into their own local issues.

4.2. External communication structures & procedures

The communication strategy also covers effective communication with parties outside the consortium, as GREAT is an Innovation in Research and Games Development that aims at reaching and engaging a broad audience to create sustainable impact.

Stakeholders will be addressed via the community engagement and communications strategy, which is coordinated in a collaborative effort by PlayMob, Leader of WP6. Details for the external communication in terms of procedures and material will be elaborated and aligned across these WPs. Bespoke communication options have been elaborated for the different target groups and deliverable D6.2 Dissemination and Exploitation Plan has been successfully completed and peer-reviewed.

4.3. Quality of deliverables and peer reviews

GREAT deliverables serve different purposes. They are a communication means within the consortium and communication with other people outside the consortium. They are aimed at transferring the know-how to exploit the results and knowledge generated by the project. Deliverables should be written with their target readers in mind. They should be concise and easy to follow, as the readability of a document is a vital ingredient for its success.

GREAT deliverables are identified in the GA as either reports or demonstrators/other. Demonstrators typically comprise software as pilots, prototypes, plan designs, design challenges, wireframes and technical platforms. They should be supported by a short documentation report.

The following general structure should be followed for deliverables in report format. This structure is also provided in the deliverable template of the project:

- Cover page
- Amendment History
- List of Authors/Contributors
- Table of Contents
- Abbreviations/Acronyms
- Executive summary
- Introductory part
- Core part
- References
- Annexes (optional)

Annex II includes a checklist that should serve as a guideline when preparing a deliverable. A GREAT deliverable may be comprised of one or more volumes and may consist of the following parts:

- The Main part is the part that summarizes the results for high-level executives, technical managers and experts with decision-making competence. It is typically one document and may contain annexes.
- Annexes are optional and have detailed technical information for experts and implementers. They are added to the main part at the end of the document.

Project deliverables may be classified according to different confidentiality levels, such as public (PU), restricted (RE) or confidential (CO). Following an open access strategy, which the project partners are committed to, all GREAT deliverables have been classified as PU regarding their dissemination level in the GA. PU means completely public access and thus, all deliverables will be made available on the project website and/or specific open repositories. In the case that consortium members want to change the level of confidentiality of any of the deliverables this requires a decision by the General Assembly and needs to be convincingly argued.

In the following, steps to be taken for publishing a deliverable are listed:

1. The deliverable development process is initiated
 - Title and description of the project deliverables are confirmed
 - The name(s) of the deliverables editor(s) are identified
 - The deliverable history document is set up, including names(s) of contributors and internal reviewer(s) in charge of the peer review for the deliverable
2. The partners appointed to generate parts of the deliverable - the authors - provide their contribution to the editor.
3. The editor(s) prepare draft 0.1 of the deliverable by assembling and integrating all contributions. This draft is discussed with all authors. It is

recommended to create the drafts directly in the shared drive and involve the internal reviewers already at this stage.

4. When the editors and the authors are satisfied with the results achieved, the editor issues draft 1.0 and puts it on the GREAT shared NextCloud folder (https://cloud.educs-hosting.net/apps/files/?dir=/EU_GREAT&fileid=1003036) and sends a note to the consortium.
5. They inform the internal reviewers and ask for a quality check, opinions and constructive comments within a defined deadline (normally one week).
6. The author(s) deals with all the comments and problems raised, if necessary, with the help of the program manager. This is a critical phase due to the many interactions involved. It may be necessary to have a meeting (audio- or video-conference) in order to speed up the process for reaching a consensus on the amendments.
7. The author(s) prepares draft 2.0, puts it on the GREAT shared NextCloud drive and informs the project manager (Dr. Jane Yau) and the whole consortium that the deliverable has reached final approved status and can be submitted to the EC and the European reviewers.
8. The deliverable is submitted to the EC portal only by the project manager.

4.4. Peer review process

One of the main methods deployed to enhance the quality of the project deliverables is an internal peer review system. GREAT deliverables will be evaluated by 2 reviewers to gather diversified and balanced viewpoints. Deliverables can be reviewed by members of the core project team or colleagues from the partner institutions as well as invited external experts by the Scientific Committee.

Peer reviewers should be nominated or volunteered at least 3 weeks before the due date of the deliverable and communicated to the consortium. Nominated peer reviewers can turn down the invitation with clear justification (e.g. lack of expertise, lack of time) and would thus be requested to nominate another candidate or any project member may also volunteer to become a peer reviewer of any Deliverable, providing that they have sufficient expertise to evaluate the Deliverable.

Confirmed peer reviewers are required to produce peer review feedback within 7-10 days after receiving the deliverable. In case of any expected delay, peer reviewers should notify the program manager immediately. During the review process, peer reviewers are encouraged to discuss the problems identified in the deliverable with the main author(s). Peer reviewers are advised to pay particular attention to the following points:

- Is the deliverable aligned with the objectives of the project and relevant work packages?

- Does the deliverable make a significant contribution to the project or not?
- Is the content of the deliverable focused on the intended purpose? Is the content of the deliverable presented in a precise and to-the-point manner?
- Is the length of the deliverable justified? Are there superfluous or irrelevant parts that should be deleted? Are there overlong parts that should be shortened? Are there any parts that are written in flowery language and/or that are unspecific or redundant?
- Are there many grammatical errors and/or typographical errors and/or incomprehensive sentences? Specifically, clear annotations indicating errors and suggested corrections are very helpful for the authors of the deliverable. The annotated deliverable may be sent back to the editor/authors via email together with the peer review report.
- Does the deliverable require substantial revision or rewriting? If yes, it will facilitate the revision process if some concrete suggestions on how to improve the deliverable are given.

Peer review results are described in a peer review report (see Annex III), which contains the following information:

- Basic information about the deliverable, author and peer reviewer
- Comments on the length and content of the deliverable
- Major strengths and weaknesses of the deliverable
- Review summary

If minor or substantial revisions are necessary, authors of the deliverable should make changes and produce the final version of the deliverable before the due submission date. The final responsibility for the content of the deliverable remains with the author(s) and it is thus their final decision about how to address and integrate the feedback from the peer reviewers. The review reports will be made available internally for the consortium only.

4.5. Quality of non-deliverables

WP6 provides a variety of presentation formats for project communication and outcomes to make sure that target groups are appropriately addressed. For non-deliverables, such as publications and dissemination material, the procedure for deliverables will be used where applicable and with a timeline that fits the material. Publications are monitored by the SC and Dissemination materials are monitored by the Editorial Board.

Since there are many types of material, this handbook cannot provide details for all cases. We distinguish the following broad categories of material.

- Dissemination material (flyer, website, leaflets, popular science publications, etc.)
- Scientific publication or conference presentation reviewed by the Scientific Committee according to focus, quality and contributions.

4.6. Internal Surveys

GREAT is committed to a continuous improvement process on the project management level. In addition to open and transparent communication and decision-making, the project management uses anonymous surveys for specific input on process management, risks and critical issues. These surveys are kept brief to ensure broad participation by each project member. The survey is distributed according to needs with no pre-defined schedule, but at least once a year (ideally before a GA meeting) to cover the following:

- Project management. In this section, participants are asked to share their positive and negative observations about the project management processes.
- Current topics. The second section focuses on topics that are currently important within the project. This can range from collaboration infrastructure to satisfaction about certain results, or specific WP-level topics. A recurring topic will be questions regarding RRI in order to sensitize project partners for the most relevant aspects for GREAT.
- Expectations and perceived risks. The third section focuses on the future and asks participants to share their perception about risks and expectations.

An essential element of this survey process is that the results are discussed and reflected upon in the consortium, preferably during a face-to-face meeting. This allows for reacting to arising issues quickly and addressing them collaboratively, e.g., by adapting the agenda.

4.7. Risk Management

As stated above, internal surveys and discussions are used to check perceived concerns and risks by all consortium partners. In addition, the updates that each WP leader gives during the bi-weekly meetings offer time and space to address also possible risks, deviations or corrective actions to be reported to the project management.

The basic risk management methodology to be followed in the project consists of the four following steps:

- Risk identification - areas of potential risk are identified and classified.
- Risk quantification - the probability of events is determined and the consequences associated with their occurrence are examined.

- Risk response - methods are produced to reduce or control the risk, e.g. switch to alternative technologies.
- Risk control and report - lessons learnt are documented.

Risks with medium or high probability and severe impact are handled with particular care during the project. At this point, it is expected that the project will safely achieve its expected results. This is also supported by the preliminary risk analysis as outlined in the grant agreement. Normal project risks are managed via good practice in project management and rely on the experience from the successful projects that the partners have previously carried out. Close supervision and tight control both by the project management and by the various committees ensure that results will be available on time and be of high quality.

Description of risk (with level of (i) likelihood, and (ii) severity: low/medium/high)	Work package(s)	Risk-mitigation measures
Not engaging stakeholders in the project. (Low, High)	2, 4, 5, 6	Proven track record of engagement amongst consortium members and focussed WPs on engagement activities
caNegative response to the project from stakeholders. (Low, High)	2, 4, 5, 6	Well-designed WP's, supplemented by domain specific knowledge and expertise within the consortium.
Not attracting Players to participate (Med, High)	2, 3, 5	Strong track record in the consortium of engaging players in games specifically in the climate domain and in broader activities.
Tech: Security Breach (Med/High)	1, 3, 4	Network protection and restricted access in place
Tech: Loss/Platform Outage (Low/High)	1, 3, 4	Auto scaling architecture and AWS cloud backup
Data: Inability to collect the right / sufficient data set (Low/Med)	1, 3, 4	Deploy alternative channels to access the data outside of quiz

Man: Inability to complete project in timescales (Low/High)	All WPs	High level of collaboration to adapt workplan activities as necessary
Loss of key team / Consortium member (Low/Med)	All WPs	Expertise is not centred in individual team members
PR Negative backlash (e.g. carbon footprint) (Low/Med)	1, 5, 6	Demonstrate industry credentials through Playing for the Planet
Env: Fire, theft, flood of equipment (Low/Low)	All WPs	Insurance and secure cloud backup
Env: Further Pandemic Lockdowns (Med/Low)	All WPs	Revert to remote working and research
Reg: GDPR Compliance Breach (Low/High)	1, 4, 5, 6	Data managed to highest levels of privacy/security
Reluctance of Policy makers to accept the findings of the project. (High, High)	All WPs	Robust and rigorous research and innovation processes embedded in the project and extensive partner experience.
Transferability of outcomes (Low/High)	All WPs	Consortium experience of partners in research, games and specific domain experience combing the three.
Ongoing effects of the Pandemic or other global emergency. (Med, High)	All WPs	The consortium has extensive experience of distance and virtual working models. WP's and tasks that have been designed to be managed flexibly (F2F or virtually)

Table 5: GREAT critical risks

The PMC will follow up on these aspects and reflect on contingencies should any of the identified risks, or emerging risks, start having an influence on the progress of activities.

During the project, project management is responsible for closely monitoring overall progress and risk identification. As part of this process project management promotes an open communication culture with open discussion of any issues arising. This strategy facilitates a full picture of the risks facing the project, and early

identification of potential challenges. The identification of risks is also elicited in collaborative reflection sessions during project meetings.

4.8. Project Templates

GREAT has established a consistent 'project style'. This is implemented by providing templates for deliverables and reports, presentations, posters, and other dissemination and communication material. More project-style templates can be produced by the communication and dissemination team, when needed. All project style templates are made available in a range of formats on the shared GREAT project NextCloud directory.

5. Tools and Collaboration Infrastructure

The previous section described the processes of communication and collaboration. However, there is also a technical component to this activity, and a number of technical tools are used to constitute the GREAT collaboration infrastructure, which is constituted by the following systems:

- The GREAT mailing list is used for project-wide asynchronous communication. The address of the mailing list is: eu_great@dipf.de
- Zoom is used for regular web conferencing (bi-weekly meetings)
- Gitlab & Wiki is used for sharing files and for real-time co-creation of documents (<https://gitlab.educs-hosting.net/eu-great/project-management/-/wikis/home>)
- Nextcloud can be used for sharing confidential, and data that needs to be protected according to data privacy regulations as defined in the Data Management Plan (https://cloud.educs-hosting.net/apps/files/?dir=/EU_GREAT&fileid=1003036)
- Google Drive can be used by partners to collaboratively work on documents and presentations (https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1gJtdsQ4Qwef1ofJjxHFn_VLKkyaCTNDr)
- E-mail, instant chat and telephone are used for bilateral communication
- GREAT Website is the main portal for presenting our work to the public (<http://www.greatproject.gg>)

The choice for this collaboration structure has been made taking into consideration practical aspects as well as privacy and data protection issues related to the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

6. Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)

6.1. What is RRI?

RRI has been formulated and widely promoted by the EC as a guiding principle and policy concept to better align science with society and to meet the so-called grand challenges. It has been promoted as a cross-cutting issue within the H2020 research programme. A widely accepted definition describes RRI as “a transparent, interactive process by which societal actors and innovators become mutually responsive to each other with a view on the (ethical) acceptability, sustainability and societal desirability of the innovation process and its marketable products” (Schomberg, 2013). Other definitions of RRI (c.f. European Commission (2013); Owen et al. (2013)) differ slightly from Von Schomberg’s, but as described by Wickson & Carey (2014) there is a consensus that RRI should (1) address significant socio-ecological needs and challenges, (2) actively engage different stakeholders, (3) anticipate potential problems and assess available alternatives and reflect on underlying values and beliefs and (4) adapt according to these ideas. Generally speaking, RRI carries out science and innovation with and for society by re-imagining the science-society relationship. According to the EC (Jacob et al., 2013), RRI comprises the following key dimensions:

1. Governance: Governance of policymakers to prevent harmful or unethical developments in research and innovation
2. Open Access: Open access to research results and publications to boost innovation and increase the use of scientific results
3. Ethics: Research must respect ethical standards and fundamental rights to respond to societal challenges
4. Gender: Gender equality and in a wider sense diversity
5. Public Engagement: Engagement of all societal actors (researchers, industry, policy makers, civil society) in a reflective research process
6. Science education: Enhancement of current education processes to better equip future researchers and society as a whole with the necessary competences to participate in research processes

In addition to these key dimensions, which are reflected in the European policy agendas, RRI can also be defined with regards to its process requirements which include openness and transparency, anticipation and reflection, responsiveness and adaptive change, and diversity and inclusion. Figure 1, which stems from the RRI-Tools project³ where ZSI has been a core partner, shows an integrative view on these two perspectives, which complement each other.

Figure 1: Overview of key dimensions

In the following, we briefly describe the six key dimensions and how they are related to GREAT.

6.2. Governance

Among the six key dimensions of RRI, governance has a function which is slightly different from the others, as it is rather an organizing and steering principle that determines the success of all other RRI dimensions. In other words, RRI relies on good governing structures for the promotion of RRI. Governance methods range from foresight techniques (scenario studies, value-sensitive design, etc.), assessment (ethical committees, needs assessment, technology assessment, etc.), agenda-setting (consultation, co-creation, etc.) to regulation (code of conduct, policies, funding guidelines, etc.).

Currently, governance of RRI is rarely seen on a project level; it is rather applied on a funding level or within organizations, e.g., to call for organization-wide RRI guidelines and policies. The GREAT project can be seen as an attempt to tackle RRI on a project level. However, comprehensive RRI guidelines for projects are still missing, and thus this handbook aims at meeting this need. Also, it has to be acknowledged that governance structures need to be at least on an institutional level in order to be sustainable. On a project level, however, it makes sense to break down what RRI in the specific context means and how it can be adapted to the project particularities.

6.3. Open access

In the narrower sense, open access is about enabling or giving access to research results and publications to the public. It addresses only the final stage of research activity, the publication, and dissemination phase. With the launch of Horizon 2020, it has become mandatory to follow open access publication strategies (European Commission, 2012).

Open access is different from open science, open innovation, and open data, although there are obvious overlaps. For instance, in contrast to open access, open science implies opening up the whole science process in real-time to the public, from choosing areas to investigate in, formulating the research questions to choosing the methods, collecting data, and finally discussing the results. Open science means democratizing science and research, usually through ICT.

When talking about open access in the context of GREAT, we refer to both open access in the narrower sense and in a wider sense of open science and open data. Our project will follow an open access publication strategy but will also make data available to the public at an earlier stage where suitable (c.f. chapter 6). There are specific platforms for sharing and we will explore how to best support and advise makers in their approach towards openness.

6.4. Ethics

The EC defines ethics as a key dimension of RRI as follows:

European society is based on shared values. In order to adequately respond to societal challenges, research and innovation must respect fundamental rights and the highest ethical standards. Beyond the mandatory legal aspects, this aims to ensure increased societal relevance and acceptability of research and innovation outcomes. Ethics should not be perceived as a constraint to research and innovation, but rather as a way of ensuring high quality results. (European Commission, 2013, p.4)

Ethics thereby shall not be perceived as a constraint but rather as a guiding principle to help ensure high quality outcomes and to justify decisions. A specific work package (WP1), and supported by WP5, is dedicated to legal and ethical aspects. We will deal with the three main aspects of ethics as defined by the EC (2015), namely 1) Research integrity and good research practice, 2) Research ethics for the protection of research objects, and 3) Societal relevance and ethical acceptability of research and innovation outcomes. This European-centered vision of ethics is used in the case of GREAT. A complementary approach that will be explored is based on the concept "design for the pluriverse" (Escobar, 2018).

Ethics further implies social justice and inclusion aspects: The widest range of societal actors and civil society shall benefit from research and innovation outcomes. In other words, products and services as a result of Research & Innovation (R&I) activities shall be acceptable and affordable for different social groups.

Ethics is an integral part of responsible research, from the conceptual phase to the publication of research results. The consortium of GREAT is clearly committed to showing appreciation of potential ethical issues that may arise during the course of

the project and has as such defined a set of procedures on how to deal with ethics in a responsible way.

The main aspects the project deals with in regard to ethics are the protection of identity, privacy, obtaining informed consent, and communicating benefits and risks to the involved target groups. The activities performed in GREAT may include data collection from individuals and organizations remotely as well as on-site. In the following, we outline the basic processes of ethical compliance of the project with a general view on the scientific data collection.

6.5. Data Protection and Privacy

During data collection process, data protection issues relating to the handling of personal data are addressed by the following strategies:

Participants, who volunteer to be enrolled in our activities, are exhaustively informed so that they are able to autonomously decide whether they consent to participate or not. The purposes of the research, the procedures as well as the handling of their data (protection, storage) will be explained. For online interviews, these explanations will be a part of the initial briefing of interviewees. For face-to-face interventions, informed consent shall be agreed upon and signed by both the study participants as well as the respective research partner.

The data exploitation will be in line with the respective national data protection acts. Since data privacy is under threat when data is traced back to individuals as they may become identifiable and the data may be abused. To mitigate this risk, we will anonymize all data. In order to ensure their fair participation through community-based research techniques, we will take advantage of the UN declaration on Indigenous People, the Nagoya Protocol, and related resources.

Data gathered through questionnaires, interviews, observational studies, focus groups, workshops, and other possible data gathering methods during research processes undertaken in this project, will be anonymized and therefore the data cannot be traced back to the individual. Data will be stored only in anonymous forms so that the identities of the participants will only be known by the research partners involved. Raw data like interview protocols and audio files will be shared within the consortium partners only after having signed the confidentiality agreement (see Annex I). Reports based on interviews, focus groups and other data gathering methods will be based on aggregated information and will comprise anonymous quotations respectively.

The collected data will be stored on password-protected servers at the partner institution responsible for data collection and analysis. The data will be used only within the project and will not be made accessible for any third party, unless anonymized. Sensitive data or personal data will not be stored after the end of the project (incl. the time for final publications) unless required by specific national legislation.

The stored data do not contain the names or addresses of participants and will be edited for full anonymity before being processed (e.g. in project reports).

6.6. Communication Strategy

Study participants will be made aware of the potential benefits and identified risks of participating in the project studies at all times.

The main means of communicating benefits and risks to the individual is the informed consent (Annex V). Prior to consent, each individual participant in any of the studies in GREAT will be clearly informed of its goals, its possible adverse events, and the possibility to refuse to enter or to retract at any time with no consequences. This will be done through a project information sheet or the informed consent form and it will be reinforced verbally.

In order to make sure that participants are able to recall what they agree upon when signing and be definitely informed about what they are agreeing to, the informed consent forms will be provided in the local language of the participant study location, with a complementary English version, if necessary. In addition, the consortium partners will make sure that the informed consent is written in a language suitable for the target group(s). Different informed consents will be made available, e.g., consent of participants in academic and non-academic contexts, or in the business or scientific contexts.

For media material (e.g. photos, videos) produced during any of the GREAT events, a media waiver form will be distributed to participants to make sure that participants are aware of this and agree/disagree with the production and use of such material by the project partners. A template for the media waiver form is provided in Annex IV of this document.

Relevant regulations and scientific standards

The consortium follows European regulations and scientific standards for the performance of ethical research, and some of the basic regulations and guidelines are detailed below.

The GREAT project will fully respect citizens' rights as reported by EGE and as proclaimed in the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union (2000/C 364/01), having as its main goal to enhance and to foster the participation of European citizens to education, regardless of cultural, linguistic or social backgrounds. Regarding the personal data collected during the research, the project will make every effort to heed the rules for the protection of personal data as described in Directive 95/46/EC5.

In addition, the consortium is adhering to the following European Regulations and Guidelines:

- The Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union:
- <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:12012P/TXT>
- European Convention on Human Rights
http://www.echr.coe.int/Documents/Convention_ENG.pdf
- Horizon 2020 ethics self-assessment
http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/portal/doc/call/h2020/h2020-msca-itn-2015/1620147-h2020_-_guidance_ethics_self_assess_en.pdf
- EU Code of Conduct:
- [https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32018D0221\(02\)](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32018D0221(02))
- European Textbook on Ethics in Research
https://ec.europa.eu/research/science-society/document_library/pdf_06/textbook-on-ethics-report_en.pdf
- European data protection legislation
- RESPECT Code of Practice for Socio-Economic Research
- Code of Ethics of the International Sociological Association (ISA)

6.7. National and Local Regulations and Standards

In addition to the more general and EU and UK guidelines, the project partners adhere to and respect national regulations and laws, as well as to ethical approval for research as requested by their own institutions. All partners are aware of their responsibilities in this respect and will follow the relevant guidelines. It should be stressed that two project partners of the GREAT consortium are located outside the European Union and additional national regulations may apply.

6.8. Gender

Gender equality generally means equal rights, opportunities, and responsibilities for both genders so that individuals can exploit and realize their full potentials independently of their gender.

Gender equality as a key dimension of RRI comprises two main aspects (European Commission, 2015), namely to strive for gender-balanced teams in research and

innovation (at operational as well as at decision-making level) and the inclusion and integration of gender perspectives in research and innovation content and process. Gender analysis and gender monitoring throughout the project shall aim at looking at both aspects of gender equality, at the human capital dimension (where possible, apart from institutional conditions), and the research aspect of gender (Föger et al., 2016).

In this project, gender is mostly relevant when it comes to internal processes, such as the composition of project teams, of work package leaders and of the scientific committee. Therefore, the use of gender-sensitive language and the awareness of producing gender-sensitive content will be emphasized. In line with the Toolkit on Gender in EU-funded research (European Commission, 2011), GREAT will strive at innovation in gender-sensitivity. Gender will be addressed and taken into account, particularly in the following project steps:

- Project design and methodology: we will make sure that in its co-design and other engagement activities, the project aims at representative data in the sense that different gender perspectives will be described, where relevant.
- Project implementation: Data-collection tools such as questionnaires, interview guidelines, etc. need to be gender-sensitive and use gender-neutral language, and have to allow for differentiation between gender perspectives. In the evaluation stage where data analysis is being undertaken, GREAT will particularly pay attention to whether there are differences between males and females, for instance, in terms of artifacts that are produced and in terms of communicating and sharing, etc.
- Dissemination phase for reporting of data: we will use gender-neutral language in our publications. Furthermore, we will sensitively decide which visual materials to use. In addition, we will aim at publishing gender-specific results.

6.9. Education

Science education under the RRI umbrella is meant to meet several objectives (European Commission, 2015; Föger et al., 2016):

- 1) To empower society to critically reflect and improve on their skills, enabling citizens to challenge research, thus to make them "science-literate" (in this respect, there is a great overlap with the key dimension of public engagement)
- 2) To enhance future researchers and other societal actors in their ability to become good RRI actors

- 3) To make science attractive to children and teenagers, and so promote science careers, especially in STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics)
- 4) To close the gap between science and education, as there is still a significant distance between the two areas.

Co-creation and co-design are identified as empowering methods as they enable participants to shape the development of technologies or services and support creative collaboration across stakeholders. GREAT has a strong commitment to co-creation processes across the various activities and this process is overall supported by WP2. In GREAT, training activities are especially foreseen in WP3 activities. They are targeted at young entrepreneurs and students related to design & arts, engineering, etc., and aim to familiarize them with ethical and technical skills and entrepreneurial aspects.

6.10. Public Engagement

In recent years, science communication has moved from the dissemination approach to informing the general public towards public engagement. This implies more elaborated and active involvement of citizens, leading to collaboration and empowerment taking place as a dialogue.

There is a vast range of tools and methods with different levels of participation available, e.g. public consultations, public deliberations for decision making, public participation in R&I processes, Citizen Science, etc. The goal of opening up research and innovation processes to the public is to better meet the values, needs, and expectations of society and thus to improve R&I and to find solutions to the so-called grand challenges that society is facing (Cagnin, Amanatidou, & Keenan, 2012).

The realization of this key dimension of RRI is an important goal in GREAT and two work packages are jointly working together to reach high quality public engagement. WP1 and WP6 are closely working on a joint strategy and have created a working team at the kick-off meeting to jointly define and execute the engagement and communication strategy of the project, via the Editorial Board.

6.11. RRI management in GREAT

The notion of Responsible Research and Innovation does not offer a checklist or one universal guideline on how to do RRI. It is also not in the spirit of RRI to have such a set of measures, as RRI is rather perceived as a process that requires continuous questioning and reflection. Thus, mechanisms have to be installed and embedded in the project to stimulate the reflection of the consortium and to keep these alive throughout the lifetime of the project.

It should be pointed out that not all key dimensions are equally relevant for GREAT as can be inferred from the discussion above. In the following, we will therefore concentrate on these key dimensions which will be dealt with in more detail. However, also the remaining dimensions shall remain in our mindsets as we would like to continuously stimulate reflection and discussion on RRI.

In order to stimulate reflection and deliberation on Responsible Research and Innovation and to keep these alive as issues in GREAT, we have distributed an Ethical and legal questionnaire: a questionnaire addressing specific ethical and legal aspects has been distributed to all project partners at the beginning of the project. Questions range from the data that is being collected and stored by project partners to the data being collected to the compliance of the platform with the GDPR as well as data subjects' rights, to be addressed by the Scientific Committee. This questionnaire especially informs the data management plan (D1.2).

To summarize, the main instruments for managing RRI in GREAT are the following:

- ethical guidelines, including forms for informed consent, code of conduct, and confidentiality agreement
- the research data management plan

7. Open Access and Open Research Data

GREAT firmly believes that openness is a major factor for innovation and this was one of the main motivations for the project. Openness has many facets. The most important ones for the GREAT consortium are, following Carlos Moedas' (European Commissioner for Research, Science and Innovation) strategy of the 3 Os, Open Science, Open Innovation and Open Data⁶:

- **Open project collaboration.** All partners are committed to developing (working) relationships with external partners for mutual benefit. Making contacts with similar projects and establishing collaboration is considered beneficial for all. Open collaboration in GREAT is understood in a trans-disciplinary way, opening innovation processes to the wider public and allowing a new form of collaboration as intended in the co-design activities of the project.
- **Open-source technology.** From a technology perspective, the project fosters sharing innovation hubs. A main aim is to share the co-designed technological artifacts with the community. Business models and exploitation strategies are not based on locking down access to project results, but on providing added value through services.
- **Open access to scientific results.** From a scientific perspective, the consortium clearly prefers open access to its scientific output, which is supported by

several project members' internal policies of supporting open access in general.

- Open access to research data. GREAT is part of a pilot action on open access to research data and is thus committed to providing access not only to project results and processes, but also to data collected during that process. Although GREAT is an innovation action according to the work program definition and not a research action, some research-related data will be collected, mainly from an evaluation perspective. Although the general policy of the GREAT project is to apply "open by default" to its research data, we have to handle privacy issues with special care. Legal rules on anonymity, as described, are thus highly relevant and need to be agreed upon with each of the participants. In case of doubt, the data privacy of our participants always prevails over the open data policy.

7.1. Open access strategy for publications and other artifacts

In line with the EC policy initiative on open access, which refers to the practice of granting free Internet access to research articles, the project is committed to following a publication strategy considering a mix of both 'Green open access' (immediate or delayed open access that is provided through self-archiving) and 'Gold open access' (immediate open access that is provided by a publisher) as far as possible.

All deliverables labelled as "public" will be made accessible via the GREAT website. The publications stemming from the project work will also be made available on the website as far as this does not infringe the publishers' rights as well as on other platforms.

All outcomes of the project, including design, protocols, databases, etc. that are labelled as "public" will be distributed under a specific free/open license, where the authors retain the authors' rights, but the users can redistribute the content freely. The following are a few relevant sources for deciding on the specific license for each outcome:

- Data:
 - A definition of Open Data:
 - Licenses:
- Software:
 - Free Software
 - The definition: Licenses:
 - Open-Source Software: The definition: Licenses:
- Reports, publications, media:
 - Creative Commons
 - Explanation:
 - Licenses:
 - Choose a license:
- Sharing publications on the project website: <https://www.greatproject.gg>

To summarize, the main open access points for GREAT data, publications, and innovation are:

- The project website: <https://www.greatproject.gg>
- Zenodo: for depositing publications (for example, <https://zenodo.org/record/7802446#.ZF5YIC0RpN0>)

7.2. Open access and open data handling process

The internal procedures to grant open access to any publication, research data, or other innovation stemming from the GREAT project (e.g. technology), follow a lightweight structure, while respecting ethical issues at all times.

The main workflow starts at the WP level, where each team is responsible for respecting ethical procedures throughout the data gathering and processing steps. The WP team members are also responsible for any data anonymization, if applicable. An agreement has to be reached within the team prior to making any outcome openly available; the final approval is given by the Project Management Committee. Due to the nature of the project, the Data Management Plan may have to be revised in the course of project activities. As the co-design approach is a dynamic methodology, it is not possible to clearly specify all data sources and collected outcomes from the beginning.

More details on all aspects related to data handling are provided in the Deliverable D1.2 Data Management Plan, which is due in Month 6.

8. Closing remarks

This handbook describes the main procedures of the GREAT project which support its effective and successful operation in order to achieve high quality project results following a RRI approach. Open access, ethics, and engagement of all societal actors are amongst the key elements of the European RRI framework (European Commission, 2012). GREAT is clearly committed to responding to societal challenges in a responsible way, both in principle and in the way the actions in the project are conducted.

While this handbook is provided in the form of a report and deliverable, it is a living document, available at: <https://docs.google.com/document/d/19uqvb6aOMLpA8S-t9PFxym0B4YDUXwD8/edit>, in the sense of being updated and challenged by the consortium in the course of the project. The processes described here are implemented in the daily work of the consortium and most of the elements (e.g., the forms for informed consent, data management plan, etc.) are separately available on the collaboration infrastructure such as the project management tool - Gitlab & Wiki.

The management reports will include updates on any crucial changes in the handbook as well as on the results of specific measures or any additional elements added to the project structure related to high quality responsible research.

9. References

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10.2. Data Exchange Form

As consortium partners in the GREAT consortium, we agree to share personal identifiable information (PII) of individuals and/or organizations as defined in the Confidentiality Agreement.

This data exchange form regulates the exchange between partners regarding sensitive data.

Researcher(s) responsible for the data (who collected the data originally)	
Type of data (e.g. interview recording, questionnaires, etc.)	
Sensitivity of data (describe briefly why this specific data is highly sensible)	
Consent form signed by all involved participants	Yes / No
Storage location	
Person(s) who have access to the data	
Purpose of sharing	
Confidentiality agreement signed	
Data retention (timeframe for storing the shared data)	

Date:

Name & Organisation:

Signature:

10.3. Data Sharing Agreement Template and instructions for use

Scope of use:

This Data Sharing Agreement template ("Template") serves to facilitate and regulate the transfer of/access to personal* data that is collected by parties of the GREAT project ("Providers") of participants and/or volunteers for the purpose of scientific research and ICT development and shared with project partners and associated partners ("Recipients").

For sake of clarity, the Template has been set up with the purpose of facilitating transfer of personal data among the partners, i.e. not including personal data; however, any Provider has no obligation to provide data requested by any Recipient. And while Provider shall seek wide implementation of the Template for the interest of scientific research, it also the case that additional requirements may be imposed in light of: (i) circumstances under which the data may have been collected and/or (ii) the limitations considered by scientific committees' custodians of data from studies.

The Template and these instructions for use are provided for informational purposes. Please refer to your institution's legal advisors for further advice and assistance when considering shipping aggregated and anonymised data at the request of a third party.

Coded data is personal data under the GDPR

The General Data Protection regulation or GDPR brings with it the obligation to investigate whether data can be transferred in fully anonymous form as this brings with it the least amount of risk. However, anonymization is not always possible and data may be shipped in coded form. Please note that merely coding personal data, for example by replacing direct identifiers with a number and storing the key in a different location in itself will not result in anonymization under the GDPR. When sharing coded data, the person sharing that data should therefore always assume that they are transferring personal data unless the local Data Protection Office(r) has explicitly confirmed that the data qualifies as anonymous data.

Legal and ethical preconditions

The shipment of personal data is subject to certain laws and regulations, which include the GDPR.

Therefore, as stated in more legal detail in the Template, explicit consent from the relevant person to whom the data relates is required, or alternatively - if consent is

not present and feasible - a documented assessment has to be made that the provision of data is legitimate, based on the ground that it serves to enable sound scientific research. In all cases, the Institution's Material and Data ethics committee should be involved and should approve the shipment. In the event that an institution has not installed a Material and Data ethics committee, that institution will have assigned the responsibility to approve shipments of data to another entity or person within its organisation.

Location of Recipient

Laws on data protection in countries outside the EU/EEA will provide levels of data protection that differ from the GDPR.

Therefore, if the Recipient is established outside the EU/EEA territory, supplementary contractual safeguards and provisions may be necessary. In such an event please contact your institution's legal advisors.

Legal name and signatures

For the correct legal name of your institution and the names of the authorised people to sign the agreement, please contact your institution's legal advisors.

AGREEMENT ON THE SHARING OF PSEUDONYMIZED PERSONAL DATA (for academic research & technical co-design)

This agreement (hereinafter referred to as "Agreement") is made and entered by and between:

<...>, <EU Country>, legally represented by the undersigned, hereinafter referred to as "PROVIDER"

and

<...>, having its principal office at <...>, <...>, legally represented by the undersigned, hereinafter referred to as "RECIPIENT".

PROVIDER and RECIPIENT hereinafter jointly referred to as "Parties" and individually as "Party";

WHEREAS

PROVIDER has obtained and / or generated DATA as further defined below;

RECIPIENT, through <...>, hereinafter referred to as “RECIPIENT SCIENTIST/DEVELOPER” , has requested PROVIDER, through <...>, hereinafter referred to as “PROVIDER'S SCIENTIST/DEVELOPER” , to provide RECIPIENT with the DATA for use by RECIPIENT’ S SCIENTIST/DEVELOPER for the purpose of its RECIPIENT’ S RESEARCH & CO-DESIGN PLAN;

The purpose and means of RECIPIENT’S RESEARCH & CO-DESIGN PLAN have been determined by RECIPIENT;

PROVIDER is willing, subject to the terms and conditions of this Agreement, to provide the DATA to RECIPIENT.

1 Definitions

DATA: the data being transferred under this Agreement is the data that is further specified in Annex I to this Agreement, provided without directly identifying personal information. The DATA constitutes pseudonymized personal data under the GDPR.

RECIPIENT’S RESEARCH & CO-DESIGN PLAN: The research and co-design plan specified in Annex II to this Agreement for which the DATA may be used.

EFFECTIVE DATE: The date of last signing of this Agreement.

INVENTION: any invention, discovery, improvement, material, signal, process, formula, know-how or other innovation related to or arising from the use of the DATA and/or CONFIDENTIAL INFORMATION , whether patentable or not and obtained as a result of the performance of RECIPIENT’S RESEARCH & CO-DESIGN PLAN.

CONFIDENTIAL INFORMATION: All information, know-how, grant applications, method of work, techniques, expertise of PROVIDER regarding the DATA, its characteristics and PROVIDER’s research concerning the DATA, whether of a scientific, technical, engineering, operational, or economic nature, supplied to or obtained by RECIPIENT in written form, in the form of drawings or in the recording of oral conversation, or samples.

GDPR: the Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data (General Data Protection Regulation)

APPLICABLE DATA PROTECTION LAW: the GDPR and any additional locally applicable data protection legislation.

SUBJECT(S): shall mean the patient or other person from whom the DATA was obtained.

II. Terms and Conditions of this Agreement:

The DATA and any other information provided is made available as a service to the research community and no ownership rights in the DATA and any other information shall be obtained by RECIPIENT under this Agreement.

DATA shall be provided by PROVIDER in a sufficiently secure manner and Parties shall handle all DATA in accordance with the APPLICABLE DATA PROTECTION LAW and shall keep such DATA confidential without any of the exclusions contained in Article 11 below.

With respect to the DATA, RECIPIENT shall be considered to be a separate data controller under the APPLICABLE DATA PROTECTION LAW for the processing of the DATA for RECIPIENT' S RESEARCH & CO-DESIGN PLAN.

RECIPIENT shall implement appropriate technical and organizational measures to meet the requirements for data controllers of the APPLICABLE DATA PROTECTION LAW.

If RECIPIENT becomes aware of a personal data breach, RECIPIENT shall promptly notify PROVIDER. In such a case Parties will fully cooperate with each other to remedy the personal data breach, fulfill the statutory notification obligations timely and cure any damages. The term 'personal data breach' refers to articles 33 and 34 of GDPR.

In the event that SUBJECT withdraws his/her permission for the use thereof, PROVIDER shall supply RECIPIENT with sufficient information and RECIPIENT shall immediately cease all use of the relevant DATA and shall delete all copies of the relevant DATA. Upon request from PROVIDER, RECIPIENT shall confirm in writing the complete deletion of such DATA.

PROVIDER shall be data controller of the DATA under the GDPR up until the moment the DATA is provided to RECIPIENT.

The Parties' contact details for inquiries regarding handling and protection of DATA are as follows:

For RECIPIENT, to:

Name:

Address:

Tel: +

Fax: +

e-mail:

For PROVIDER, to:

Name:

Address:

Tel: +

Fax: +

e-mail:

RECIPIENT shall not carry out any procedures with the DATA, such as linking, comparison, processing, with which the identity of the Subject could be derived. The RECIPIENT and the RECIPIENT SCIENTIST/DEVELOPER agree that the DATA: (a) is to be used only for the academic purposes as described in RECIPIENT' S RESEARCH & CO-DESIGN PLAN; (b) will not be used for other, including commercial purposes. Furthermore, in carrying out the RECIPIENT' S RESEARCH & CO-DESIGN PLAN, RECIPIENT shall not allow third parties that are not expressly mentioned in the Annexes to access or otherwise process the DATA without prior written approval of PROVIDER. However, as an exception to the foregoing, such prior approval shall not be required for service providers in the context of the standard business operations of RECIPIENT, such as parties who supply ICT infrastructure maintenance. RECIPIENT will safeguard that any data processors who have access to the DATA are instructed by a binding agreement to process the personal data in accordance with the requirements stated in the GDPR.

[OPTION: Notwithstanding the restrictions on transfer given directly above, RECIPIENT may transfer the DATA to academic third parties solely for the purpose of replication of the RECIPIENT' S RESEARCH/CO_DESIGN PROJECT, in conformance with the data and replication policies of a journal that published the results of RECIPIENT' S RESEARCH/CO-DESIGN PROJECT. Such transfers shall only be made by RECIPIENT after the conclusion of a written agreement with terms at least as strict as the terms of this Agreement and without any further right of transfer.

Upon request, RECIPIENT' S SCIENTIST/DEVELOPER shall keep PROVIDER' S SCIENTIST/DEVELOPER informed of the results arising from RECIPIENT' S RESEARCH & CO-DESIGN PLAN.

RECIPIENT will report any INVENTIONS to PROVIDER and PROVIDER' S SCIENTIST/DEVELOPER. RECIPIENT shall promptly provide PROVIDER with a detailed written description of the INVENTION and indicate the role, if any, of any of RECIPIENT' s employees in creating the INVENTION. Ownership of INVENTIONS will follow inventorship. Where ownership of any INVENTIONS vests in RECIPIENT, PROVIDER shall have a perpetual nonexclusive royalty free license to use such inventions for its internal research and teaching purposes. In the event the INVENTION is a joint INVENTION, both Parties shall make appropriate mutual arrangements concerning the protection and exploitation of such joint INVENTION. Until such agreement is effective, each Party shall be entitled to use the joint INVENTION for research purposes, but neither Party shall be entitled to exploit, disclose, license or transfer its rights in connection with the joint INVENTION.

Except as provided in this Agreement, no express or implied licenses or other rights are provided to the RECIPIENT under any Intellectual Property (IP) rights of PROVIDER.

The DATA will be provided at no cost or with an optional transmittal fee solely to reimburse PROVIDER for the collection and/or preparation of the DATA. If a fee is requested, the amount will be indicated here: <...>. RECIPIENT will pay the transmittal fee within forty five (45) days from the date of receipt of a valid invoice thereto. Payment will be made to a bank account in the name of the PROVIDER, as set out in the invoice.

DATA will be provided to the RECIPIENT by PROVIDER' s SCIENTIST/DEVELOPER in a sufficiently secure manner and in a format to be agreed upon by the RECIPIENT SCIENTIST/DEVELOPER and the PROVIDER' s SCIENTIST/DEVELOPER.

PROVIDER warrants a) that it has verified that there is an appropriate legal ground for the provision of the DATA to RECIPIENT in accordance with the GDPR (such as Article 6 and/or 5.1 sub b GDPR) b) that there is a valid exception to the prohibition for processing personal health data (Article 9 GDPR) and c) that it shall be provided under approval from the relevant ethics committee to the extent required. Apart from this, it is expressly understood that PROVIDER does not make any warranties regarding the DATA and specifically does not warrant or guarantee that the DATA will be accurate, be merchantable or useful for any particular purpose. PROVIDER cannot and shall not be held liable for any claims or damages by RECIPIENT or any third party, in connection with or as a result of the use of DATA by RECIPIENT. Unless and to the extent caused by PROVIDER' s gross negligence or willful misconduct, RECIPIENT undertakes to hold harmless PROVIDER at all times against all of such damages or claims.

In regards to the DATA and personal data breaches, RECIPIENT shall be responsible and liable for any damages, losses and fines resulting from its own actions or failures to adhere to the terms of this Agreement and APPLICABLE DATA PROTECTION LAW and RECIPIENT shall indemnify and hold harmless PROVIDER for any of such damages. For the purposes of this sub clause, actions or omissions of data processors contracted by RECIPIENT, shall be attributed to RECIPIENT.

RECIPIENT agrees in its use of the DATA to comply with all applicable international and national laws, statutes, regulations and guidelines.

RECIPIENT shall treat all CONFIDENTIAL INFORMATION as confidential for the duration of this Agreement including any extension thereof and thereafter for a period of five (5) years following termination or expiry of this Agreement. Excluded from this obligation of confidentiality shall be any CONFIDENTIAL INFORMATION of which the RECIPIENT can reasonably demonstrate that it (a) was previously known to RECIPIENT, or (b) is, and/or becomes, publicly available during said five (5) year period through no fault of RECIPIENT, or (c) is independently and lawfully developed by the RECIPIENT, or (d) was published or otherwise disseminated in accordance with the publication procedure set out below in article 12. However, the foregoing exceptions shall not apply to: (a) CONFIDENTIAL INFORMATION contained within more general information that may fall within one or more of the exceptions, or (b) any combination of features or items of CONFIDENTIAL INFORMATION where one or more of the relevant individual features or items (but not the combination itself) may fall within one or more of the exceptions. The obligation of confidentiality shall not apply to any disclosure required by law, provided that RECIPIENT shall notify PROVIDER of any disclosure required by law in sufficient time so that PROVIDER may contest such requirement, if PROVIDER so chooses.

Parties acknowledge the importance of disseminating the results of the RECIPIENT'S RESEARCH PROJECT. Therefore, RECIPIENT shall endeavour to publish or otherwise publicly disclose information, any data, results or information generated using the DATA ("Disclosure(s)"), after review by PROVIDER. The following shall apply to Disclosures:

Authorship of any publications shall follow the principles set out in the ICMJE recommendations 'Defining the Role of Authors and Contributors' as can be found on <http://www.icmje.org/recommendations/browse/roles-and-responsibilities/defining-the-role-of-authors-and-contributors.html> .

At least thirty (30) days before RECIPIENT submits a paper or abstract for Disclosure, RECIPIENT shall provide such paper or abstract to PROVIDER, who will have thirty (30) days to review proposed manuscripts and fifteen (15) days to review proposed abstracts to assure that it's CONFIDENTIAL INFORMATION is protected.

It is agreed that RECIPIENT will fully comply with any reasonable written request by PROVIDER to omit specified CONFIDENTIAL INFORMATION of PROVIDER from such paper, abstract, press release or other disclosure prior to Disclosure.

In every Disclosure by RECIPIENT based upon results obtained from the research through the help of the received DATA provided by PROVIDER, RECIPIENT shall appropriately acknowledge PROVIDER and PROVIDER'S SCIENTIST as contributor of the DATA.

This Agreement will become effective on the EFFECTIVE DATE and will terminate [···] years after the EFFECTIVE DATE, unless mutually extended in writing by both Parties. Any clauses which will be expected or intended by its nature to survive the termination or the expiration of this Agreement, shall survive the termination or the expiration of this Agreement.

Upon expiration or termination of this Agreement, the right to use the DATA and CONFIDENTIAL INFORMATION will automatically end. [OPTION 1: After expiration or termination of this Agreement, RECIPIENT will destroy all DATA received from PROVIDER. Upon request from PROVIDER, RECIPIENT shall confirm in writing the complete deletion of such DATA and CONFIDENTIAL INFORMATION.] [OPTION 2: However, RECIPIENT may retain one copy of the DATA solely to comply with DATA transfer requests that third party academic institutions may make for replication of the RECIPIENT'S RESEARCH/CO-DESIGN PROJECT, as described in Article 3 above]

This Agreement will be construed, governed, interpreted and enforced according to the laws of the Netherlands. Parties will first strive to settle any disputes amicably before taking legal action. All disputes arising out of or in relation to this Agreement that cannot be settled amicably will be brought before the competent court in the regarding European Country, in the district in which the Provider resides.

This Agreement will be binding upon and inure to the benefit of the respective successors and assignees of the Parties hereto. However, RECIPIENT may not assign this Agreement in whole or in part without the prior written consent of the PROVIDER.

This Agreement may only be altered or amended by an instrument in writing signed by all of the Parties.

If any portion of this Agreement is in violation of any applicable regulation, or is unenforceable or void for any reason whatsoever, such portion will be inoperative and the remainder of this Agreement will be binding upon the Parties.

Both Parties acknowledge that the signatories to this Agreement are authorized representatives of each of the Parties and legally authorized to sign this Agreement.

If the lawful performance of any part of this Agreement by a Party is rendered impossible by or as a result of any cause beyond such Party's reasonable control, such Party will not be considered in breach hereof as a result of failing so to perform.

IN WITNESS WHEREOF, the Parties have executed this Agreement, in duplicate originals or as a signed PDF, as of the Effective Date.

For the PROVIDER

By: _____

Name:

Title

Date: _____

By: _____

Name:

Title

Date: _____

READ AND ACKNOWLEDGED:

PROVIDER'S SCIENTIST

For RECIPIENT,

By: _____

Name:

Title

Date: _____

By: _____

Name:

Title

Date: _____

READ AND ACKNOWLEDGED:

RECIPIENT'S SCIENTIST

ANNEX I to the Data Sharing Agreement template

Description of the DATA, methods of transfer and storage, allowed processors

Data subjects

The personal data transferred concern the following categories of data subjects:

Purpose of the transfer(s)

The transfer is made for the following purpose (see Annex II to the Data Sharing Agreement template):

Categories of data

The personal data transferred concern the following categories (types) of data:

Sensitive data (if appropriate)

NB: All health information qualifies as sensitive data as meant in the field below, e.g.:

- racial or ethnic origin,
- political opinions,
- religious or philosophical beliefs,
- trade union membership,

- genetic data, biometric data,
- health data,
- sex life and sexual orientation

Method of transfer

e.g.: Soft- or hardware encrypted USB drive, database entry such as in Castor, etc.

Method of data storage and security measures (e.g. method of encoding)

Authorized processors, if applicable, as indicated in clause 3 of the Agreement

ANNEX II

Recipient's research & co-design plan

11. Annex II – Checklist for Deliverables

1. Overall technical evaluation of the deliverable
 - 1.1. Does the deliverable contain new, or value added information?
 - 1.2. Are there any major technical errors, omissions, lack of necessary details?
 - 1.3. How do the results compare with the state of the art and/or parallel activities?
 - 1.4. What value does the document add to the project partners?

2. Executive summary
 - 2.1. Are the questions addressed by the deliverable clearly stated and answered?
 - 2.2. Which problem(s) and key questions of interest to intended readers are addressed?
 - 2.3. What are the main expected benefits of this deliverable?
 - 2.4. What are the results contained in this deliverable?
 - 2.5. Who are the main consumers for this deliverable, e.g. who should read it?
 - 2.6. Why should I read the deliverable?
 - 2.7. Suggestions/recommendations for follow-up actions by project participants and/or by general public.
 - 2.8. Is the length acceptable for the executive summary (e.g. approx. 2 pages)?

3. Introduction
 - 3.1. Is the purpose of the document clearly stated?
 - 3.2. Is the technical subject properly introduced?
 - 3.3. If necessary, is there a guide to the reader (document structure, short description of chapters and relationships)?
 - 3.4. If necessary, are there statements on technical assumption, readers' prerequisites, and relationships with other documents or parallel activities?

4. The main part of the deliverable
 - 4.1. Does it contain what was defined in the deliverable description in the DoA?
 - 4.2. If something has been left out, have clear and valid reasons been given as to why?
 - 4.3. Is the key part structured in a logical way?
 - 4.4. Is the content appropriate for the intended audience? Does it only include essential information?
 - 4.5. Does it duplicate or contradict standards or other on-going known initiatives? If yes, the affected standard or initiatives need to be identified.
 - 4.6. Is the length acceptable (approx. 30 pages for main part)?

5. Conclusion

5.1. Are conclusions reached? Are they within the consortium perspective?

5.2. Are any necessary follow-up actions clearly indicated?

5.3. Are the conclusions consistent with the executive summary?

5.4. Should this Deliverable be

5.4.1. Utilised by other projects?

5.4.2. Released (in full or part) to the Associated Partner Network?

6. Annexes (optional)

6.1. Are the annexes complete in all parts?

6.2. Are the annexes relevant to the content of the deliverable?

12. Annex III Peer Review Template

Instructions: Peer reviewers should fill out all six sections in this template and send the completed template to the main author on or before the specified due date.

1. Basic Information

- Deliverable Number & Title:
- Main Author/Editor:
- Peer Reviewer (Institution, Person):
- Date of Receipt of Deliverable:
- Date of Sending out the completed peer review:

2. Length of the deliverable

- Is the length of the deliverable justified? - YES - NO
- If no, please specify by e.g. indicating parts that are superfluous, irrelevant, redundant, unspecific or would need more explanation?

3. Content

- Does the deliverable meet the objectives of the deliverable described in the respective Work Package Work Description? - YES - NO
 - If not, please indicate the parts where improvement is necessary.
- Is the content of the deliverable focused and presented in a precise and to-the-point manner? - YES – NO
 - If not, please indicate the parts where improvement is necessary.
- Does the deliverable require substantial revision or rewriting? - YES - NO
 - If yes, please give concrete suggestions how to improve the deliverable.

4. Major strengths

5. Major weaknesses

6. Review Summary

The current version of the deliverable is []:

1. applicable and ready to be submitted to the EC, if required
2. applicable, but requires minor revisions
3. inapplicable and requires substantial revisions.

Is it necessary for the revised deliverables to be reviewed again before submitting it to the EC

(1:Yes, 2: No)? []

13. Annex IV – Consent Form

Photograph, Video or Audio Recording Consent Form

I, _____ (recorded/photographed person’ s full name), do hereby consent to the use by _____(entrant’ s full name) of my image, video, voice, or all three of them, in the item described above.

Fill-out only in case of a child photographed/recorded:

I, _____ as the legal representative of _____ (recorded/photographed child’ s full name), do hereby consent to the use by _____ (entrant’ s full name) of my image, video, voice, or all three of them, in the item described above.

In addition, I waive any right to inspect or approve the finished video recording.

I agree that all such pictures, video or audio recordings and any reproduction thereof shall remain the property of the author and that the EU & UKRI may use it as it sees fit.

I understand that this consent is perpetual, that I may not revoke it, and that it is binding.

I understand that these images may appear publicly as part of GREAT project website and/or other marketing materials.

Name: _____

Date of Birth (DD/MM/YYYY): ____ / ____ / ____

It is understood that this material will be used in a legitimate manner, both internally and outside EU and is not intended to cause any harm or undue embarrassment to the parties involved.

Signature: _____

Date (DD/MM/YYYY): ____ / ____ / ____

